

IMPACT OF DIABETES MANAGEMENT ON THE PROGRESSION OF DIABETIC KIDNEY DISEASE

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Abstract

Introduction

Diabetic kidney disease (DKD) is a serious complication of diabetes mellitus (DM) and remains a leading cause of end-stage renal disease (ESRD) worldwide. This prospective cohort study aims to examine the effect of diabetes management on the progression of DKD.

Methods

This study was designed as a prospective cohort study, involving 200 patients diagnosed with DKD. Patients were divided into well-controlled (HbA1c < 7%) and poorly controlled (HbA1c ≥ 7%) groups. The estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR), serum creatinine, and urinary albumin-to-creatinine ratio (uACR) were recorded at baseline and during each monthly follow-up appointment throughout the 12-month study period.

Results

Patients having HbA1c less than 7% (n = 72) showed slower decline of estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR, 2.1 ± 0.9 mL/min/1.73 m²). Pearson's correlation analysis demonstrated a strong inverse association between HbA1c levels and eGFR (r = -0.72, p < 0.001). Patients with HbA1c levels greater than 7% experienced a major increase in uACR measurements from 280 mg/g to 620 mg/g. The change in uACR was smaller for patients with HbA1c values less than 7%, whose uACR levels decreased from 240 mg/g to 370 mg/g (p = 0.004).

Conclusion

This study provides strong evidence that diabetes management slows kidney function decline and decreases the risk of DKD progression.

INTRODUCTION

Diabetic kidney disease (DKD) is a serious complication of diabetes mellitus (DM) and remains a leading cause of end-stage renal disease (ESRD) worldwide.¹ Diabetes-related nephropathy develops in approximately 40% of patients with diabetes mellitus (DM), affecting both type 1 (insulin-dependent) and type 2 (non-insulin-dependent) DM.² DKD is defined as decreased kidney function in patients who are

diabetic, determined by persistent albuminuria and progressive decline in glomerular filtration rate (GFR), with no indication of alternative kidney disease.³ DKD leads to both renal structural and functional changes. These pathological changes are associated with various clinical stages of disease progression. Early clinical evidence of DKD begins with glomerular hyperfiltration and rising GFR; this

is followed by the development of microalbuminuria and progresses to macroalbuminuria accompanied by a declining GFR and overt proteinuria, eventually leading to ESRD.¹

Long-standing hyperglycemia is a main contributing factor to disease onset and progression in DKD patients. It triggers both hemodynamic and metabolic disturbances in the body that activate various pathophysiological pathways, further exacerbating DKD.⁴ Early renal histological changes are largely attributed to glomerular hyperperfusion and hyperfiltration. The process underlying glomerular hyperfiltration in hyperglycemic states involves multiple overlapping pathways and mediators that drive pathogenic progression. Elevated plasma glucose concentration also upregulates glucose-dependent effects, thereby increasing GFR via afferent arteriolar dilation. This response is facilitated by a range of vasoactive mediators, including nitric oxide (NO), insulin-like growth factor 1 (IGF-1), transforming growth factor β (TGF- β), vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF), glucagon, and prostaglandin.^{4,5}

Under similar conditions, augmented sodium-glucose cotransporter 2 (SGLT2) reduces distal solute delivery to the macula densa, which perceives this as low filtration and activates the tubuloglomerular feedback (TGF) mechanism. This results in dilation of the afferent arteriole and is accompanied by a subsequent rise in intraglomerular pressure and GFR, as renal autoregulation is disrupted.⁶ At the same time, activation of the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system (RAAS) and increased formation of angiotensin-II (ANG-II) cause efferent arteriolar constriction. Thus, the concurrent presence of afferent arteriolar dilation and efferent arteriolar constriction further amplifies glomerular hypertension. Beyond its hemodynamic role, angiotensin-II is known to exert numerous nonhemodynamic effects that are implicated in the progression of DKD. These include glomerular hypertrophy via activation of MAPK pathways, extracellular matrix (ECM) accumulation through upregulation of TGF β -1, reactive oxygen species (ROS) formation mediated by NADPH oxidase activation, as well as contribution to podocyte injury, endothelial dysfunction, proteinuria, inflammation, and fibrosis.^{7,8} Endothelin-1 (ET-1), a vasoactive peptide produced by endothelial cells, is another potent vasoconstrictor of the renal efferent arteriole,

often mimicking and synergizing with RAAS to promote renal injury and progression of DKD.⁹

On the other hand, metabolic changes associated with diabetes further advances kidney injury. These recognized metabolic pathways induce inflammation, oxidative stress, endothelial dysfunction, and cellular damage. They involve promoting intracellular mechanisms such as hyperglycemia-induced formation of advanced glycation end products (AGEs), activation of protein kinase C (PKC) pathway, upregulation of the polyol pathway, activation of the DAG-PKC pathway, and excess reactive oxygen species (ROS) production.^{10,11,12} The cumulative effects of these hyperglycemic-induced processes give rise to major structural changes in the kidneys, the earliest being thickening of the glomerular basement membrane. This is followed by mesangial matrix expansion, loss of podocytes with fusion of their foot processes, glomerulosclerosis, and eventually tubulointerstitial fibrosis. These renal changes are irreversible and contribute to the gradual decline in kidney function, ultimately leading to ESRD.¹²

DKD is a lifelong, consequential disease accompanied by high morbidity and mortality rates.¹³ While there is no cure, substantial evidence indicates that early intervention can prevent or delay disease onset and progression. The pathophysiological processes underlying DKD showcases the necessity of proper diabetes management in the prevention of disease progression and overall clinical outcome.¹⁴ Onset and progression of DKD can only occur in the presence of hyperglycemia, hence, intensive glycemic control remains the main target for current therapeutic strategies. Strict control of glucose levels shows reduced incidence of micro- and macroalbuminuria, delayed GFR decline, and a slower progression to ESKD.^{12,15} Recent findings also suggest that regulation of blood lipids, normalization of blood pressure, the use of selective pharmacological therapies, and lifestyle modifications, including dietary sodium and protein restrictions, regular physical activity, weight loss, and smoking cessation are all important in lowering the risks of diabetes in DKD.^{16,17}

Diabetes-related complications are projected to be the seventh leading cause of mortality by 2030, and the global prevalence of diabetes is expected to reach 783 million cases by 2045.^{18,19} However, the full impact of

diabetes and associated DKD is likely underestimated, as the majority of DKD patients die from cardiovascular complications and microvascular events before progressing to ESRD.²⁰ DKD causes significant health and financial burdens and the prospect of reducing this burden exists across all stages of disease progression. Understanding the pathogenic processes of DKD and advancing new therapeutic strategies is needed to effectively address the disease. The aim of this prospective cohort study is to examine the effect of diabetes management on the progression of DKD. We also note that effective control of blood glucose and comprehensive screening for DKD may lower the risk of DKD development and DKD-related complications.

Methods

Setting and Participants

This prospective cohort study was designed to investigate the impact of diabetes management on kidney disease progression in patients with DKD. The study was conducted at outpatient clinics in Saidu Teaching Hospital, Swat, Pakistan, and involved 200 participants. Their kidney function was monitored and recorded each month throughout a 12-month follow-up period using clinical and laboratory parameters. Each patient's first available kidney function test and the date it was taken were set as the baseline measurements and index date, respectively. These were used to detect patients who had early to moderate DKD and to monitor the disease progression.

Patients aged 18 and above who had been diagnosed with DKD were eligible to participate. Presence of DM (type 1 and 2) was confirmed according to the American Diabetes Association criteria: characterized as A1C $\geq 6.5\%$, a fasting blood glucose level ≥ 126 mg/dL, a non-fasting blood glucose level ≥ 200 mg/dL, or the use of glucose-lowering medication. Inclusion parameters in this study were baseline kidney function assessments such as estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) and urinary albumin-to-creatinine ratio (uACR). Patients that were eligible had an eGFR between 30 and 89 mL/min/1.73 m², indicating DKD stages 2 to 3b, and a uACR of ≥ 30 mg/g, indicating moderately increased albuminuria. Patients were required to initiate management for diabetes as per standard

clinical practice. This included antihyperglycemic drugs such as insulin, metformin, glucagon-like peptide (GLP-1) receptor agonists, dipeptidyl peptidase-4 (DPP-4) inhibitors, sodium-glucose cotransporter-2 (SGLT2) inhibitors, or any other clinically indicated agent.

Patients with a prior history of non-diabetic kidney disease i.e., glomerulonephritis, polycystic kidney disease, IgA nephropathy, or lupus nephritis, were excluded from the study. Those who experienced an episode of acute kidney injury (AKI) during the 6-month period before the index date were also not enrolled. Patients who were taking nephrotoxic medication, such as non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), aminoglycosides, ACE inhibitors, or iodinated contrast agents, around the time of enrollment were not allowed to participate. This reduced confounding factors that could independently affect kidney function and ultimately study results. Patients who did not have the corresponding clinical information available from previous medical records were also excluded. This study was conducted in accordance with institutional and international ethical standards. All participating patients gave their written informed consent.

Data Collection and Variables

Data collected for this study was completed by a well-coordinated process of clinical examinations, patient medical records, and laboratory tests conducted at Saidu Teaching Hospital, Swat, Pakistan. Participants were interviewed for complete medical and family histories along with socioeconomic status. Specifically designed questionnaires were used to document their biodata, medical history (including any allergies and medications), treatment adherence, and lifestyle behaviors.

Demographic variables were recorded during baseline assessments including age, sex, body mass index (BMI), duration of DM, as well as baseline eGFR. Anthropometric measurements, such as height, weight, body circumferences (e.g., waist, hip, and limbs), and blood pressure (BP), were obtained and used to calculate BMI. BP was measured by the auscultatory method using a mercury sphygmomanometer and was an average of two readings.

Overnight-first void urine and serum samples were collected early in the morning after an overnight fast. Biomarkers from urine and serum samples from baseline and follow-up visits were used to assess DKD progression. The Chronic Kidney Disease Epidemiology Collaboration (CKD-EPI) equation was used to calculate eGFR and uACR was used to calculate albuminuria.

Potential contributing factors and comorbidities such as dyslipidemias, hypertension, and cardiovascular disease were noted. For this study, hypertension was defined as having a systolic blood pressure > 140 mmHg, and/or a diastolic blood pressure > 90 mmHg, or the use of antihypertensive medications.

Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistics were used to evaluate patient characteristics within the study. We expressed continuous variables as means \pm standard deviation (SD) and categorical variables as frequencies and percentages. To analyze changes in kidney function between baseline and 12 months, paired t-tests were applied for normally distributed variables and Wilcoxon signed-rank tests were applied for non-normally distributed variables. The change in kidney function, specifically eGFR and uACR, was calculated for each patient, and Pearson or Spearman correlation coefficients were used to compare baseline HbA1c and kidney function decline. Patients were also classified as having good glycemic control (HbA1c < 7%) and poor glycemic control (HbA1c \geq 7%). Their kidney function decline was then compared using Mann-Whitney U tests. The risk of DKD progression for patients with HbA1c < 7% compared to those with HbA1c \geq 7% was estimated as adjusted hazard ratios

(HRs) with 95% confidence interval (CI) by using Cox proportional hazards regression model. The model was adjusted for age, sex, BMI, duration of diabetes, and baseline eGFR. We conducted all statistical analysis using IBM SPSS Statistics, version 26 (IBM Corp.), and a p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

Demographic Variables

In total, 200 patients were enrolled at Saidu Teaching Hospital, Swat, Pakistan, with a confirmed DKD diagnosis and followed for a 12-month study period. Among the participants, 114 (57%) were male and 86 (43%) were female. The average BMI for the entire sample population was 28.6 ± 4.2 kg/m². The median duration of diabetes was 12.4 ± 5.6 years. The mean HbA1c during baseline was $7.8 \pm 1.4\%$, with 128 (64%) having an HbA1c \geq 7%, indicating poor glycemic control.

Glycemic Control and Kidney Function Decline

Patients with an HbA1c < 7% (n = 72) showed a gradual eGFR decline (2.1 ± 0.9 mL/min/1.73 m²) during the follow-up period. While patients with an HbA1c \geq 7% (n = 128) showed an accelerated eGFR decline (5.8 ± 1.7 mL/min/1.73 m²; p < 0.001). The rate of eGFR decline was lower for those with good glycemic control. Serum creatinine levels were increased in poorly glycemic-controlled participants, from 1.3 ± 0.4 mg/dL to 1.9 ± 0.6 mg/dL. In contrast, only a slight increase in serum creatinine levels, from 1.2 ± 0.3 mg/dL to 1.4 ± 0.3 mg/dL (p = 0.002), was seen in good glycemic-controlled participants, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The relationship between glycemic control and kidney function decline.
Abbreviations: HbA1c, glycated hemoglobin.

Figure 2. Albuminuria and HbA1c correlation
Abbreviations: HbA1c, glycated hemoglobin.

Albuminuria and HbA1c Correlation

The study demonstrated a positive correlation between albuminuria and elevated HbA1c levels ($r = 0.72$, $p < 0.001$). Patients with an HbA1c $\geq 7\%$ had an increase in uACR, from 280 mg/g to 620 mg/g. Change in uACR was lower for patients with an HbA1c $< 7\%$, increasing from 240 mg/g to 370 mg/g ($p = 0.004$), as shown in Figure 2.

Progression to Advanced Diabetic Kidney Disease

During the study, 37 (28.9%) patients from the poor glycemic control group progressed to advanced DKD (eGFR < 30 mL/min/1.73 m²). Whereas only 9 (12.5%) patients from good glycemic control group

progressed to advanced DKD ($p < 0.01$). Risk of disease progression to advanced DKD was higher in patients with an HbA1c $\geq 7\%$. An adjusted hazard ratio (HR) of 2.5 (95% CI 1.8–3.9, $p < 0.001$) for the development of advanced DKD was observed in those with HbA1c $\geq 7\%$.

Lipid Profile, Blood Pressure, and Comorbidities

Patients with poor glycemic control had a significantly higher mean systolic blood pressure (142.5 ± 12.8 mmHg) compared to patients with good glycemic control (135.2 ± 10.3 mmHg, $p = 0.03$). Similarly, the poor glycemic control group had 15% higher LDL-C

levels and a greater prevalence of hypertension and cardiovascular disease.

Discussion

In this prospective cohort study, we investigated the association between diabetes management and the progression of diabetic kidney disease (DKD). We found the risk of DKD progression was significantly lower in patients who had undergone diabetes treatment and achieved good glycemic control (HbA1c < 7%). These patients showed a slower rate of decline in kidney function compared to those with poor glycemic control (HbA1c \geq 7%). Diabetes management also contributed to a decreased risk of progressing to advanced stages of DKD. These results remained significant following adjustments for age, sex, BMI, duration of diabetes, and baseline eGFR. Findings of this study indicate that intensive glucose control plays a role in slowing DKD progression.

Onset and progression of DKD can only occur in the presence of hyperglycemia. Even in the earliest stages of hyperglycemia, patients can still present with a relatively high risk for DKD.²¹ This is demonstrated throughout our study, as patients with HbA1c \geq 7% had a significantly greater mean decline in eGFR (5.8 ± 1.7 mL/min/1.73 m²) during follow-up in comparison to those with HbA1c < 7% (2.1 ± 0.9 mL/min/1.73 m², $p < 0.001$). This interpretation is consistent with those of previous studies that recognize the importance of glycemic control in the management of DKD. An inverse correlation ($r = -0.72$, $p < 0.001$) between hyperglycemia and kidney function shows the effect of glycemic control on kidney disease outcomes. The correlation is attributed to several hyperglycemic-induced pathogenic mechanisms seen in DKD, including glomerular hyperfiltration, oxidative stress, inflammation, and fibrotic changes.⁴ Similar findings have also been reported in several cohort studies, suggesting HbA1c \geq 7% is associated with a greater decline in kidney function.^{22,23}

Among other biomarkers, albuminuria was also used to evaluate disease progression. Study results showed change in albuminuria was much greater in patients with poorly controlled blood glucose compared to those with well-controlled blood glucose. During the 12-month follow-up period, we observed an increase in uACR (from 280 mg/g to 620 mg/g) in patients

with an HbA1c \geq 7%, while patients with an HbA1c < 7% had a lesser increase (from 240 mg/g to 370 mg/g). The positive correlation ($r = 0.68$, $p < 0.001$) between albuminuria and HbA1c levels further solidifies the effect of diabetes management on disease progression in DKD. This observation is parallel to findings of other clinical trials and meta-analyses, such as DCCT and UKPDS, that confirm good glycemic control can significantly regress albuminuria and halt DKD progression.^{24,25} In this respect, treatment of hyperglycemia, with the goal of achieving HbA1c levels below 7%, should be pursued as early as possible to slow progression of DKD, including the onset of microalbuminuria and progression to overt nephropathy.

Over the course of our study, we observed that 28.9% of patients with HbA1c \geq 7% progressed to advanced DKD, stages 4 and 5. In contrast, only 12.5% of patients with HbA1c < 7% progressed to advanced stages. The finding that HbA1c \geq 7% was an independent predictor of increased kidney function decline (adjusted HR 2.5; 95% CI 1.8–3.9, $p < 0.001$) was clinically relevant. Further findings from the study found participants with poor glycemic control exhibited higher mean systolic blood pressure and low-density lipoprotein cholesterol (LDL-c) levels. It is suggested that DKD be regarded as a coronary heart disease risk equivalent, largely due to the higher rates of microvascular and cardiovascular events in DKD patients, particularly when hyperglycemia is not treated.²⁰ In light of these findings, diabetes management should include blood glucose regulation and concurrent management of blood pressure and lipids. To address potential clinical gaps, clinicians should prioritize implementing multifactorial and personalized treatment strategies that account for patient-specific factors. This approach will improve outcomes in DKD and reduce the risk of cardiovascular events.

Our study confirms the importance of blood glucose management in DKD progression. The findings of this association have been consistent among several other longitudinal cohort studies.^[22-25] In agreement with our results, these studies have reported intensive diabetes management slows the rate of kidney function decline in patients with DKD. However, such studies were centered around either eGFR or albuminuria as indicators of disease progression. Our

study examines both biomarkers for a more inclusive understanding of how variables, such as kidney functional and structural damage, can influence DKD progression. Results also indicated that poor blood glucose control in the absence of clinically manifest DKD, even in the earliest stages of the disease, may result in lasting disturbances in the kidney. Early intervention and tighter glycemic control remain central focuses in attenuating the progression of these pathological changes. However, whether glucose control alone is adequate in the treatment of DKD warrants additional investigation.

Strengths and Limitations

Our study had several advantages. Firstly, data was collected at multiple predetermined times (baseline and 3, 6, 9, and 12 months) during scheduled follow-up visits. Longitudinal trends in eGFR, uACR, creatinine, and so forth were able to be recognized throughout different stages of DKD. Secondly, patients were separated into good glycemic control (HbA1c < 7%) and poor glycemic control (HbA1c ≥ 7%) groups. Rather than assessing absolute HbA1c values, specific glycemic targets were established for patients, making it simpler to check trends and patterns. Thirdly, our cohort solely enrolled early-to-moderate staged DKD patients, where the focus was on disease progression as patients entered later stages of DKD. Lastly, recent cohort studies have hinted at effective diabetes management slowing DKD progression; however, those studies focused on either eGFR or albuminuria as indicators for disease progression. Our study had the advantage of investigating both biomarkers (eGFR and albuminuria) for a more complete understanding of DKD outcome.

Limitations of this study was having a sample size of 200 participants restricted to a single institution. Subgroup analyses were hard to conduct given lack of genetic and geographical diversities. We could not assess correlation variations across different ethnic and cultural populations, or geographic locations.

Conclusion

This prospective cohort study provided evidence that suggests intensive diabetes management is associated with a significantly slower rate of diabetic kidney disease (DKD) progression. The study dissected the

prognostic role of blood glucose levels in DKD patients for a 12-month period. Over the course of the study, individuals with well-controlled blood glucose levels (HbA1c < 7%) demonstrated a reduced rate of decline in kidney function and a lower progression to advanced stages of DKD compared to patients with poorly controlled blood glucose levels (HbA1c ≥ 7%). These patients presented with a slower decline in glomerular filtration rate (GFR), reduced albuminuria, and decreased incidence of advanced renal complications relative to the comparison cohort group. Our findings suggest that diabetes management should be added to the list of clinical priorities in patients at risk for DKD. It also confirms the importance of blood glucose management in patients with DKD. Future guidelines should consider classifying diabetes as a DKD risk equivalent with the considerable evidence substantiating the high risk of DKD events in people with diabetes.

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